

PREDICTING THE THROUGH-THICKNESS ENHANCEMENT OF Z-PINNED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

To improve the delamination resistance in fiber-reinforced composite laminates, several through-thickness reinforcement (TTR) techniques have been developed, e.g. stitching [1], tufting [2-3], Zanchoring [4-5] and z-pinning [6]. Z-pinning refers to the insertion of short, discontinuous rods which are inserted in the through-thickness direction of prepreg composite laminates. The z-pins exert traction forces (via a combination of adhesion and friction) that suppress the crack opening displacement, retard delamination growth and enhance the effective delamination toughness [7-8]. Z-pins, which are supplied in a square pattern via a low density foam (preform) carrier, are inserted into a prepreg laminate using a high frequency ultrasonic hammer prior to the curing process. After the insertion process, the remaining part of the preform and z-pin is sheared off and the laminated composite is cured in an autoclave. The z-pin is characterized by the material, length, diameter (typically 0.2 – 1.0 mm) and areal density (typically 0.5 – 4.0%). The mechanisms of crack bridging have been investigated for a variety of z-pin materials such as pultruded carbon-fiber composite, glass-fiber composite and titanium alloys [8].

Only a relatively small volume fraction of z-pins is needed to significantly enhance the through-thickness properties and damage tolerance. Studies have shown an improved resistance to compression after impact damage and delamination static/fatigue crack growth due to z-pin reinforcement [10-11]. However, the presence of the pins creates resin pockets and disrupts the alignments of the fibers (creating regions of localized waviness) and can significantly degrade the in-plane properties, such as tensile and compressive strength, by as much as 30%

[12]. This significant trade-off between in-plane properties and improvement in delamination resistance dictates that z-pins should only be selectively inserted in areas ‘vulnerable’ to delamination propagation.

Currently, industrial applications of z-pinned components remain limited. Manufacturing of z-pinned components have followed a somewhat ad-hoc approach which is largely based on limited experimental characterization. The lack of technical standards has consequences for life prediction and design of certifying tests for the structural integrity of z-pinned components [13]. Furthermore, lab-based coupon testing of pinned laminates may produce non-conservative predictions for delamination resistance for a given configuration but show different fracture characteristics in a structure of different scale, geometry or loading [13].

Thus, comprehensive design strategies and tools which can predict the inter-laminar failure under various loading and environmental conditions are important to bring z-pins to a higher level of technological maturity. A number of approaches have been presented in the open literature for predicting the resistance to delamination in z-pinned composite laminates. Analytical micro-mechanical constitutive models which implicitly relate the bridging forces to the crack opening displacement have been presented for mixed-mode loading cases. A generalized micro-mechanical analytical model was developed by Cox [14] to describe the behavior of through-thickness bridging tows when inclined to the fracture plane and subject to mixed-mode loading conditions. This model was employed by Zhang [15] to predict the Mode I response of double cantilever beam (DCB) pinned specimens using the finite element (FE) method. Allegri and Zhang [16]

presented a micro-mechanical model which represented the reinforcing tow as a rigid rod embedded in a Winkler type linear elastic foundation. The derived bridging force-displacement map was subsequently implemented in FE analyses of cruciform joint configurations via non-linear springs. Bianchi and Zhang [17] have recently implemented bi-linear cohesive zone formulations at discrete pin locations where the Mode I z-pin bridging action is governed by a traction-separation law derived from a meso-mechanical model of the pin pull-out process. This work was further extended to mode II loading conditions [18], in which a micro-mechanical constitutive model was implemented which describes the reinforcing tow as an Euler-Bernoulli beam embedded in a Winkler elastic foundation. To account for the mode II toughness enhancement of the pins, discrete cohesive zone elements were implemented in FE analyses of end-notched flexure (ENF) reinforced specimens with encouraging results.

Nevertheless, theoretical derivations and the numerical implementations of these approaches have been primarily geared towards one specific mode of delamination (UD dominated stacking sequence) and an expansion of these techniques for modeling mixed-mode type delamination using one set of parameters is not yet available in a general numerical framework.

A complete mapping of the large-scale bridging effect as a function of loading regime, material geometry and structural configuration requires a multi-scale approach. In this paper, an effective and robust multi-scale modeling tool is presented that combines the classical cohesive finite element (FE) methods with a semi-analytical TTR constitutive model.

2 Modeling strategy

The modelling strategy employed in this research is presented in Fig 1. A micro-mechanical constitutive bridging model of through-thickness pins subjected to mixed-mode loading is derived to obtain the bridging law. The model is calibrated by means of the apparent fracture toughness data obtained from experimental mixed-mode single z-pin pull-out tests.

The resultant bridging law is then implemented into special-purpose cohesive zone elements for macro-scale finite element analysis, see Fig 2. This cohesive element offers the flexibility to employ two cohesive laws concurrently, for the pinned and unpinned region. The goal is to derive a single set of z-pin parameters and a mixed-mode bridging map which can be implemented for all loading cases in a FE numerical framework.

2.1 Micro-mechanical constitutive bridging model

The experimental details of this strategy presented in Ref [9] and the analytical model are briefly described here.

Extensive experimental work has been performed to characterize the damage tolerance capability of z-pinned reinforced composite laminates. Work carried out at the University of Bristol [9] has characterized the pull-out response of single z-pinned laminates (uni-directional, quasi-isotropic, zero-dominated and cross-ply) under mode I, mixed-mode and mode II loading conditions. The experimental data of apparent toughness against mode-mixity reveals that a transition region exists where the behavior of the z-pins shifts from complete pull-out (low mode-mixity) to pin fracture due to combined tension and bending (high mode-mixity). This transition region is difficult to quantify since a large standard deviation is reported for the experimental test data; attributed to the variability in the insertion misalignment angles and residual curvature of the z-pins.

The micro-mechanical model represents the bridging tows as Euler-Bernoulli beams undergoing small but finite rotations upon elastic deformation. It is assumed that the beams are orthogonal to the delamination crack plane. The beams are embedded in a Winkler type linear elastic foundation, as in Bianchi and Zhang [18]. The pin fracture is taken into account by using a Weibull strength criterion. This allows the transition from complete pull-out to pin fracture with increasing mode mixity, which is associated with a decrease in apparent inter-laminar fracture toughness, to be captured. It is postulated that the pure mode II response can be entirely attributed to the fracture toughness associated with the tensile fibre failure of the bridging pin under

bending loads. The system of non-linear differential equations is numerically solved as a boundary value problem in MATLAB. The z-pin axial (Z), transverse (X) and bending (M) bridging forces are expressed as a function of pull-out displacement (η) and transverse sliding displacement (ΔU). The bridging forces and associated displacements are stored in lookup tables, from which interpolated values of $Z(\eta, \Delta U)$, $X(\eta, \Delta U)$ are calculated during FE analyses. Furthermore, the model takes into account asymmetric pull-out behaviour of z-pins and is valid for brittle fibrous rods.

The differential solution of the bridging forces is found by discretizing the normalized pull-out displacement d and mode-mixity \bar{f} ranges in such a manner that for each value of \bar{f} , d increases incrementally. This numerical procedure is performed until the bridging pin satisfies the fibre failure criterion or complete pull-out is achieved. Input parameters which relate to the intrinsic material properties of the z-pin or geometrical configuration are known ‘*a priori*’ or can be assumed from values published in the open literature. However, parameters corresponding to the ‘disturbed’ pinned laminate are not known and need to be estimated by means of a parallelized genetic algorithm (GA). The 6 calibrated input parameters are related to the foundation stiffness provided to the bridging tow by the embedding laminate, the frictional properties at the pin/resin pocket interface during pull-out and the strength and fracture of single z-pins. This micro-mechanical bridging model is calibrated by means of the apparent fracture toughness data obtained from mixed-mode pull-out testing of single carbon/BMI z-pins inserted into a quasi-isotropic laminate. As shown in Fig 3, the model is able to reproduce the correct trend of the apparent toughness as function of the mode-mixity.

2.2 Implementation to cohesive zone element formulation

The implementation of the micro-mechanical constitutive bridging law is achieved via means of continuum based cohesive elements written in a user-element subroutine (VUEL) in ABAQUS\Explicit. The user-defined cohesive elements are implemented as sets of continuum

elements which represent the unpinned and pinned region. The formulation currently only allows non-zero-thickness (continuum) elements.

An explicit code is chosen to overcome some of the inherent convergence difficulties that can be encountered during material softening. For cases when failure and material degradation can occur, an explicit scheme is more favorable since it can handle large changes in the stiffness matrix compared to an implicit analysis. Since, the bridging length of the inserted z-pins is of the order of magnitude of the laminate thickness, an explicit scheme was considered more favorable to avoid severe convergence issues.

The unpinned cohesive zone model is governed by the laminate intrinsic toughness and behaves according to a mixed-mode bi-linear traction-separation law as implemented by Jiang et al [19]. The energy dissipated during the crack opening is controlled via a constitutive formulation that uses a simple damage variable combined with a simple bilinear softening cohesive-decohesive law that relates the interfacial traction components (σ) the relative displacement components (δ).

The z-pin bridging map, as shown in Fig 4, is stored as an array of facets and points. At each time increment, the bridging stresses are interpolated from the “nodal” (points) values of the facet on which the mixed-mode relative displacement δ_m can be projected, see Fig 5.

3 Model verification

3.1 Experimental tests

The efficacy of this modeling strategy is evaluated by the simulation of double cantilever beam (DCB) and mixed-mode bending (MMB) specimens, both pinned and unpinned, using FE analysis. 64 plies of carbon-reinforced IM7/8552 were manufactured in which the stacking sequences for the full laminate were $[(0/-45/90/45)_{4s}]_s$. Mechanical properties are given in Table 1. The z-pins are made from pultruded T300/BMI. The specimens have an initial crack a_0 formed by inserting a thin PTFE film in the mid-plane of the specimen before curing. In the

pinned laminate configuration, the z-pinned region covers 22.75 mm in length and spans the entire width of the specimen. Having an unreinforced region gives a clear indication of the bridging effect of the pins once a crack has initiated and propagated during testing. The DCB configuration is shown in Fig 6.

MMB tests are popular mixed-mode fracture toughness tests since they easily facilitate the setup of different loading conditions using the same geometry of specimens. The loading conditions are defined by the linear relationship of three different displacement points (Δ) of the specimen [20]:

$$\Delta_{LP} = \left(\frac{c}{L}\right)\Delta_I + \left(\frac{c+L}{L}\right)\Delta_M \quad (1)$$

In Eqn (1), L refers to half the specimen length, c is the length from the point of load application to the mid-point of the specimen. Different mixed-mode conditions can be obtained by varying the length c , based on the following relationship:

$$c = \frac{L\left(\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3\left(\frac{1-\phi}{\phi}\right)} + 1\right)}{3 - \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3\left(\frac{1-\phi}{\phi}\right)}} \quad (2)$$

The MMB test apparatus is illustrated in Fig 7; the initial crack length a_0 is 25 mm, the first unpinned length is 10 mm followed by a pinned region of 22.75 mm. The mixed-mode (ϕ) loading cases considered are $\phi = 22\%$, 43% and 66% corresponding to a lever length c of 101, 57.5 and 41 mm, respectively.

These tests allow the validation of the tool to a configuration in which the damage mechanisms is predominantly large-scale bridging without any other interaction with intra-laminar damage mechanisms.

3.2 Macro-scale model description

Based on previous modeling experience and to reduce the computational running time, a simplified ‘unit strip’ model was developed which represents approximately a single row of 7 pins. The cohesive

element formulation effectively ‘smears’ the periodic pin arrangement across the elemental area, hence individual modeling of the pins is not required. The unpinned and pinned regions are modeled using the same cohesive element formulation (VUEL) simply by activating (or deactivating) the appropriate resin/pin feature. Moreover, 8-node continuum shell elements SC8R with reduced integration and hourglass control are used to model the composite laminate beams, which accurately capture the laminate rotations. A schematic of the modeling setup for the DCB and MMB test cases are shown in Fig 8 and 9. The in-plane cohesive element size is determined such that there are 4-5 elements within the fracture process zone. The cohesive element length used is 0.5 mm for all simulations, the upper bound of acceptable simulation results for the cohesive properties given in Table 2. Only one element per unit width was defined in the model since the crack propagation is orthogonal to this direction.

The loading velocity defined in all solutions is approximately 1 mm/s (defined initially by a smooth ramp rate followed by a constant velocity) which produced satisfactory results in regard to insignificant dynamic effects. Furthermore, mass scaling was used to accelerate the solution time and no damping was used in the models.

Element deletion was not active in these models since the cohesive elements have an in-built penalty stress algorithm to resist interpenetration of crack faces once an element has failed. These pseudo-failed elements do not have the ability to carry stress or contribute to the stiffness matrix; however they allow the visualization of state dependent variables and negate the need of surface-to-surface contact algorithms.

3.2 Numerical results

3.2.1 DCB Results

A comparison of the numerically calculated force vs. applied displacement with the tests results for a pin aerial density of 2% and pin diameter $d = 0.28$ mm is presented in Fig. 10. An initial linear elastic response is observed for both pinned and unpinned

specimens. The onset of delamination growth is similar for both tests cases, regardless of the presence of the pins, indicating that the initial fracture toughness (an intrinsic material property) is controlled by the resin-rich interfacial properties. For the unpinned specimens, a monotonic, continuous load drop characterizes the propagation of the delamination crack which continues to grow until it has reached the full length of the specimen. For the pinned specimens, following a small load drop as the crack tip propagates through the unpinned region, the crack reaches the first row of z-pins. Here, the pins begin to exert traction forces which bridge (or partially suppress) further crack opening displacement, characterized by a gradual increase in the global force response. Since the pins are discrete entities embedded in the composite laminate, it is appropriate to refer to this phenomenon as ‘apparent toughness’ since it cannot be attributed to any intrinsic material properties. Very good agreement is obtained with the experimental data.

3.2.1 MMB Results

The results of several MMB simulations, using the same set of input parameters and bridging map, is shown in Fig. 11. Again very good agreement is obtained, giving confidence that the developed z-pin cohesive element tool is capable of modeling mixed-mode response of pinned composite laminates without any additional calibration.

Conclusions

In this paper, a comprehensive numerical framework is presented in which user-defined cohesive elements have been developed to simulate the large-scale bridging response of through-thickness-reinforced composite specimens. This is achieved by successfully integrating a micro-mechanical constitutive bridging model into the element formulation. The micro-mechanical model describes the mixed-mode loading behavior of through-thickness pins as Euler-Bernoulli beams embedded within a Winkler elastic foundation. It is assumed that the pin is inserted orthogonal to the delamination plane. Moreover, asymmetric pull-out response is also included to account for

delaminations not acting in the mid-plane of the pin. This constitutive model is valid for a general mixed-mode regime.

The validity of the constitutive model is confirmed against single z-pin tests in quasi-isotropic composite laminates which are subject to mixed-mode loading conditions. Following a general algorithm optimization technique, six independent parameters are calibrated which are intrinsic to the composite laminate configuration. The model successfully captured the trend of apparent toughness of the pins against the mixed-mode loading angle. From a small number of discrete data points, a continuous bridging map was derived.

Special user-defined cohesive elements were developed which are capable of describing both the resin-rich interface layer and the large-scale bridging mechanism of the pins. At each time increment, the mixed-mode displacement of the cohesive elements is interpolated across the continuous bridging map, stored as an array of facets and points, from which the mixed-mode bridging stresses can be obtained. The model is validated by comparing finite element predictions with mixed-mode fracture toughness tests under quasi-static loading conditions. Good agreement with experimental data was obtained, thus demonstrating the cohesive element’s capability of simulating the mixed-mode response of through-thickness reinforced composite specimens based on a single set of parameters.

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Fig 1 Modeling strategy using an integrated experimental-analytical-finite element approach

Fig 3 Apparent fracture toughness of single Z-pin coupons normalized for a 2% aerial density versus mode-mixity. Results from the calibrated model are shown in red.

Fig 2 Schematic of cohesive element formulation with cohesive and z-pin interface features (all shear displacements are mode II, i.e. $\delta_1 = \delta_2$)

Fig 4 3D z-pin bridging map of axial force (Z) as a function of opening (η) and sliding (ΔU) displacements

Fig 6 Geometry and dimension of the z-pinned DCB test specimen (unit: mm).

Fig 5 Mixed-mode z-pin bridging law. The bridging stresses are interpolated from the “nodal” (points) values of the facet on which the mixed-mode relative displacement δ_m can be projected

Fig 7 MMB test configuration

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Fig 8 Simplified unit strip FE model representation of DCB specimen using 3 shell elements through thickness of each composite beam and cohesive elements at interface (whole model included for comparison).

Fig 9 3D FE-model of a MMB specimen

Fig 10 Comparison between DCB experimental and numerical prediction (Z-pin configuration: 2% aerial density and $d = 0.28$ mm).

Fig 11 Comparison of numerical z-pin model with experimental data of DCB & MMB tests with different % mode II mixity.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of IM7/8552 prepreg

E_1	E_2	E_3	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}
GPa	GPa	GPa	-	-	-	GPa	GPa	GPa
161	11.38	11.38	0.3	0.3	0.45	5.17	5.17	3.92

Table 2 Cohesive zone model parameters used in this study

G_{IC}	G_{IIC}	$\sigma_{I\max}$	$\sigma_{II\max}$	E_I	E_{II}
(N/mm)	(N/mm)	(MPa)	(MPa)	N/mm^3	N/mm^3
0.21	1.0	30	60	1e5	1e5